

CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING AND PRIVACY-PRESERVING TECHNOLOGIES FOR 6G

D6.1 PLAN FOR DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION INCLUDING COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	Fifth Generation
6G	Sixth Generation
SNS	Smart Networks and Services Industry
AI/ML	Artificial Intelligence Machine Learning
API	Application Programming Interface
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
CORD	Central Office Re-architected as a Datacenter
CLAIRE	Confederation of Laboratories for Artificial Intelligence Research in Europe
DIDs	Decentralised Identities
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FHE	Fully Homomorphic Encryption
FL	Federated Learning
H2020	Horizon 2020
HW	Hardware
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
NDM	Nokia Data Marketplace
NFV	Network Functions Virtualization
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
ODL	OpenDaylight
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
O-RAN	Open Radio Access Network
OSF	OpenStack Foundation
OSM	Open Source MANO (Management and Orchestration)
OTA	Over the Air
Ph.D.	Doctor of Philosophy
PU	Public
RATS	Remote Attestation Procedures
RIS	Reconfigurable Radio Systems
SA	Security for AI
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TRL	Technology Readiness Levels
VM	Virtual Machine
WP	Work Package
XMSS	Extended Merkle Signature Scheme
ZKP	Zero-knowledge Proofs

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document presents the detailed plan for dissemination, communication, and exploitation of the CONFIDENTIAL6G project. The plan outlines the strategies and activities that will be undertaken to effectively communicate the project's results, share knowledge with the wider community, and maximise the commercial potential of the project outcomes. By implementing this plan, the project aims to create a lasting impact beyond its duration and contribute to the overall objectives of the Horizon Europe program.

The plan encompasses three main components: exploitation, dissemination and communication activities. The dissemination activities will ensure that the project's outcomes reach the relevant target groups through various channels such as conferences, workshops, publications, and social media. The goal is to facilitate the widespread dissemination of knowledge generated by the project and foster engagement with key stakeholders.

Exploitation activities will focus on identifying and pursuing the commercial potential of the project outcomes. By leveraging the innovative solutions developed within the CONFIDENTIAL6G project, efforts will be made to explore business opportunities, industry collaborations, and technology transfer.

Communication activities are designed to engage with target groups and the wider public, increasing awareness of the project's research and its significance. Through strategic communication efforts, including target group mapping, key message identification, and the development of communication materials, the project aims to effectively convey its objectives, findings, and societal impact. Ongoing monitoring and evaluation will ensure the effectiveness of the communication strategies and allow for adjustments when needed.

The success of this plan relies on the collaborative involvement of all project stakeholders, including project partners, researchers, industry experts, policymakers, and the general public. By fostering a coordinated effort, the plan will optimize the reach and impact of the project's outcomes.

The CONFIDENTIAL6G project recognizes the importance of communication and dissemination in achieving the desired impact of the research. Aligned with the principles of the Horizon Europe program, this plan will ensure the successful implementation and sustainability of the project. Through effective dissemination, exploitation, and communication of the project outcomes, the CONFIDENTIAL6G

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project will contribute to the creation of a sustainable and competitive European research and innovation ecosystem.

In conclusion, the Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation Including Communication Activities is a vital deliverable for the CONFIDENTIAL6G project. By implementing this plan, the project aims to disseminate its outcomes effectively, explore commercial opportunities, and create a lasting impact. Through targeted communication efforts, the project will increase awareness, engage with stakeholders, and contribute to the overall objectives of the Horizon Europe program.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 SCOPE

In this section the purpose of the document is described. In the CONFIDENTIAL6G project, Work Package 6 (WP6) plays a crucial role in ensuring the project's impact by closely engaging with diverse stakeholders and existing ecosystems from its inception. WP6 focuses on communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, implementing an effective strategy for bootstrapping and expansion. This strategy relies on communication, dissemination, and exploitation efforts to ensure the widespread recognition and adoption of the project's scientific and technological outcomes.

The objective of this deliverable, **D6.1**, is to develop a comprehensive plan for communication, dissemination, and exploitation within WP6. The plan defines a communication strategy, creating assets and materials, bootstrapping and expanding the project's ecosystem, and ensuring its long-term sustainability. Furthermore, it involves disseminating the scientific and technological outcomes through relevant conferences, workshops, journals, and engaging with standardization bodies and forums. Additionally, WP6 aims to support the commercial exploitation of project results by developing and evaluating appropriate business models and formulating an exploitation strategy that safeguards intellectual property rights.

To effectively execute these objectives, we will leverage best practices and methodologies tailored to the unique needs of the CONFIDENTIAL6G project. Our plan includes the establishment of a project-specific communication plan and the creation of assets and materials that align with the project's goals. We will focus on bootstrapping and expanding the project's ecosystem to foster sustainability beyond the project's duration. Furthermore, we will actively support the commercial exploitation of project results through the development and evaluation of appropriate business models, ensuring the protection of intellectual property rights.

1.2 DOCUMENT ORGANISATION

The document is organised into several sections, each addressing specific aspects of the project's communication and dissemination strategy:

- Section 1 - Introduction: this section provides an overview of the document's scope.

- Section 2 - Engagement and Methodology: This section describes the approach used to engage with the project's target stakeholders.
- Section 3 - Dissemination Strategy and Plan: This section outlines the strategy and plan for disseminating the project's outcomes.
- Section 4 - Communication Strategy and Plan: This section details the communication plan implemented within the CONFIDENTIAL6G project.
- Section 5 - KPIs and Project Monitoring: This section discusses the key performance indicators (KPIs) used to monitor the project's progress in terms of dissemination, exploitation and communication activities.
- Section 6 - Exploitation Strategy and Plan: This section presents the strategy and plan for exploiting the project's outcomes commercially.
- Section 7 - Key Exploitable Results: This section identifies and highlights the key results that can be exploited from the project.
- Section 8 - IPR Knowledge Management: This section focuses on the management of intellectual property rights (IPR) within the project.
- Section 9 - Conclusion: This section provides a summary and conclusion of the document.

2 ENGAGEMENT METHODOLOGY

2.1 CONFIDENTIAL6G TARGET ENGAGEMENT APPROACH

CONFIDENTIAL6G acknowledges the significance of efficient communication and dissemination in accomplishing project objectives. The success and impact of a project heavily rely on effectively managing target groups and reaching out to the intended audience. Hence, it is crucial to tailor the target group engagement strategy to meet the specific needs and preferences of each group. By actively engaging with these target groups, CONFIDENTIAL6G can foster awareness, garner support, and ensure the utilisation of research findings for positive outcomes in relevant domains. In the following sections, we will outline our engagement methodology, encompassing distinct phases and the identification of target groups.

Phases of Engagement

To foster growth and cultivate productive collaborations throughout the project's duration, we will implement an Agile Stakeholder Engagement Framework. This methodology aims to continuously enhance and strengthen our interactions with key target groups, empowering the program as outlined in the Grant Agreement. The framework comprises three iterative phases, each spanning six months, progressively reinforcing target group engagement.

The initial phase involves scouting and evaluating target groups, identifying specific candidates aligned with the project's objectives and anticipated impact. Leveraging the consortium members' prior experiences and involvement in related initiatives, as well as potential leads generated through second-degree partnerships and the outcomes of interaction phases, such as emerging Horizon projects, lays a robust foundation for engagement. This phase culminates in the creation of a Target Groups Map, visually presenting key actors and specific candidates, organising and correlating these audiences, and establishing a shared terminology for project reference. Communication activities, including the planning of all project-related endeavours, setup of primary communication tools and channels (e.g., Website, Social Media), and identification of potential target groups and stakeholders, will commence during the first communication phase, starting in M1 of the project. Stakeholder identification will remain an ongoing process throughout the project, allowing for flexibility to adapt to changing circumstances. Initial communication efforts, such as press releases, will also be initiated in this phase.

The second phase revolves around active engagement with the identified target groups, supporting the activities outlined in our Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation strategies. CONFIDENTIAL6G will collaborate with relevant initiatives specialising in industrial digitization, and when appropriate, formally participate in specific Task Forces, Working Groups, contribute to scientific publications, and engage in events. Building upon feedback from previous iterations, we will continually refine and enhance the efficiency and impact of these measures. The second phase will emphasise early communication activities to promote the project's existence and forthcoming initiatives to a broader audience and specific communities. Special emphasis will be placed on online tools and measures, leveraging their extensive reach compared to traditional approaches. Networking for webinars or other online events, generating articles about the project across the internet, and undertaking relevant communication activities will be the primary focus during this phase. This communication phase will persist throughout the project, aiming to disseminate general project information to a wide range of stakeholders.

The third phase concentrates on extracting insights from interactions and gathering valuable external feedback to inform subsequent iterations. This entails obtaining insights through consultations, employing methods such as quick questionnaires or interviews. The third communication phase will finalise around M8 when the project reaches a relative level of maturity, and initial concrete outcomes are achieved. Targeted communication activities will be conducted during this phase, including the creation and dissemination of articles, blogs, or posts specifically highlighting project outcomes and benefits. Hosting or participating in online (or physical, if feasible) events to communicate CONFIDENTIAL6G's innovations, as well as producing targeted communication materials like videos for the community, will be key activities during this phase. Simultaneously, Phase 2 will continue, focusing on communicating general aspects of the project to a broad stakeholder base.

By adopting this comprehensive engagement approach, CONFIDENTIAL6G aims to foster meaningful connections with target groups, maximise the project's impact, and facilitate the utilisation of research outcomes. Throughout the project's lifecycle, we remain dedicated to refining our strategies, leveraging valuable feedback, and adapting to evolving circumstances.

2.2 CONFIDENTIAL6G STAKEHOLDERS

Industry (Telecom operators, Service providers)

The industry, including telecom operators and service providers, forms a significant target group that can exploit CONFIDENTIAL6G solutions for confidential communications enhancing privacy and security of the services provided to meet existing or future needs. Engaging with this sector is vital for project dissemination and communication. Telecom operators and service providers are interested in innovative solutions and partnerships that can enhance their services and offerings. Collaborating with industry players can lead to valuable partnerships, increased visibility, and the potential for commercialization. By targeting the industry, the project can establish credibility, gain access to resources, and ensure the relevance and applicability of its outcomes within the business landscape.

Developer community

The developer community, comprising software engineers and programmers, is a crucial target audience. Engaging developers fosters collaboration, attracts contributors, and gathers valuable feedback. They actively participate in conferences, hackathons, and online forums, offering expertise and opportunities for project growth.

Academia

Academia, comprising universities, colleges, research institutions, and individual researchers, is a key target audience for research project dissemination. Engaging academia creates collaborations, increases visibility, and enhances credibility within the scientific community. They attend events, seek publications, webinars, and newsletters to stay informed about the latest research findings and network with peers.

Policymakers

Engaging policymakers is crucial for project communication. By influencing regulations and policies, policymakers impact project implementation. Building relationships and effectively communicating findings and recommendations can align project outcomes with policy priorities and contribute to evidence-based decision-making. The main policymakers of the project are EU Commission; Regulators; Public Agencies; Observatories/Think Tanks. CONFIDENTIAL6G will strive to reach this target group to showcase how they can benefit from the solutions implemented.

Partnerships & Networks

This target group includes Horizon Europe Partnerships, EU Technology Associations, EU Digital Innovation Hubs, Digital Europe Programme, H2020 Projects, BDVA, CLAIRE, etc. CONFIDENTIAL6G aims to harness the knowledge and capacity of initiatives around cryptography, confidential computing, privacy preserving technologies, blockchain, federated AI/ML for 6G. The project will leverage the consortium's participation in active ecosystems to create synergies, extending the collaboration across the digital technology providers and the use-cases domains. Related segments will include (1) European partnerships emerging from Horizon Europe; (2) EU-wide associations related to cryptography, confidential computing, privacy preserving technologies, blockchain, federated AI/ML for 6G; (3) ecosystems concentrating large communities of private-sector organisations, generating value and upscaling the competitiveness of SMEs, including data and industry- oriented EU Digital Innovation Hubs; (4) previous projects driving missions in the aforementioned areas.

Society, Non-scientific community

The non-scientific community, encompassing society at large, is an important target group for project communication and dissemination. This group consists of individuals who may not have a scientific or technical background but are impacted by the project's outcomes or can benefit from its results. Engaging with the non-scientific community helps raise awareness, foster understanding, and gather support for the project. By effectively communicating the project's objectives, benefits, and potential impacts in a relatable and accessible manner, the project can generate interest, garner public support, and ensure its societal relevance. Engaging with this community can be achieved through public outreach initiatives, public events, media coverage, and targeted communication channels to ensure that project outcomes are accessible and beneficial to a wider audience.

2.3 CONFIDENTIAL6G FOCUS GROUPS

To foster active involvement from the intended audience, T6.2 aims to establish a dynamic focus group from external specialists selected from diverse target groups. These dedicated focus groups assume a pivotal role in tailoring the project's communication and dissemination endeavours to cater to the distinct requirements and interests of the intended audience. Through this approach, they ultimately amplify the project's impact and success. The insights and feedback provided by CONFIDENTIAL6G participants will assist the project team in refining their

communication and dissemination strategy to engage the target groups more effectively. Moreover, these proficient experts will provide valuable suggestions and guidance to the consortium, leveraging their professional expertise to further advance the project's objectives.

Following an internal analysis, the CONFIDENTIAL6G consortium collectively concluded that the focus group would comprise four members, selected from the following categories or domains representing the target groups:

1. IoT
2. Privacy
3. 6G and Cloud
4. Cybersecurity
5. Standardisation

The chosen focus group members should demonstrate a proactive attitude, possess strong technical and security backgrounds, and have prior experience participating in EU projects. These qualifications ensure their ability to readily comprehend the project and its objectives, enabling them to make an immediate impact. The responsibilities of the CONFIDENTIAL6G focus group members include:

- Familiarizing themselves with the project and its objectives.
- Participating in consortium meetings, held once per year.
- Attending the consortium meetings.
- Presenting their perspectives on the project, offering professional insights and recommendations to the consortium regarding areas of focus that align with the project's objectives.

2.4 CONFIDENTIAL6G STAKEHOLDERS MAP

CONFIDENTIAL6G stakeholders are being mapped to understand a level of engagement and importance of each target group. The Stakeholders Map (Figure 1) is created that graphically summarises the main target audiences at this stage. The graphical illustration has been defined by taking into consideration the different target groups identified, which will serve as a start base for tailored and specific campaigns, and communication and dissemination activities of the project. The figure provides a framework for managing target groups based on interest and influence as:

- Y-axis depicts the “Power” potential of the project to this target group and vice versa
- X-axis depicts the “influence” that the target group may have towards our project and vice versa.

Figure 1. CONFIDENTIAL6G Stakeholder map

Manage Closely Quadrant

The "Manage Closely" quadrant encompasses stakeholders from academia who hold significant influence over the project and possess a strong interest in its outcomes. These target groups, consisting of academic institutions, researchers, and scholars, play a vital role in the project's success. It is essential to engage them early on and maintain frequent communication to actively incorporate their valuable feedback and insights throughout the project's duration.

Keep Satisfied Quadrant

In the "Keep Satisfied" quadrant, the key stakeholders include industry players such as telecom operators and service providers, as well as the developer community. While policymakers and decision-making authorities fall into this category, their availability and active engagement in the project may be limited. Despite the challenges in maintaining regular communication with this group, it is important to consider their feedback and align the project's activities with their directives. By

addressing their interests and ensuring their satisfaction, the project can foster positive relationships and garner support from these influential stakeholders.

Keep informed Quadrant

In the "Keep Informed" quadrant, there are stakeholders such as policymakers, as well as other organizations or individuals directly associated with the project, such as other projects or initiatives. While these stakeholders may have limited impact or influence on the project's outcomes, it is still valuable to explore opportunities for joint communication and dissemination efforts. By engaging in collaborative activities, such as sharing information, insights, and best practices, these stakeholders can stay informed about the project's progress and contribute to a broader exchange of knowledge and ideas.

Monitor Quadrant

The current quadrant encompasses partnerships, networks, and societal stakeholders, as well as the non-scientific community, who may have low influence on the project activities and limited availability to actively engage in project-related tasks. While these target groups are not expected to be heavily involved in the project activities, it is important to maintain regular communication with them. By staying in frequent contact and remaining vigilant, the project can ensure that any shifts in their engagement level or movement to other quadrants are promptly identified. This proactive approach helps in keeping these stakeholders informed and fostering potential opportunities for collaboration and participation in the project.

3 DISSEMINATION STRATEGY AND PLAN

The dissemination strategy and plan for Project CONFIDENTIAL6G aims to effectively communicate the project's results to the target groups, creating awareness, understanding, and encouraging action. The plan will utilise a range of tools and activities to disseminate results to target groups, achieving them through traditional and social media.

The plan adopts a comprehensive 4-step approach that revolves around the key questions of "*what, when, to whom, and how?*". This approach is designed to ensure effective outreach throughout the project, with partners encouraged to follow all the steps, select relevant aspects, and augment their efforts to maximise audience engagement.

The project has established predefined dissemination objectives that are closely interlinked with communication objectives and the overall project goals. The aim is to create a significant impact beyond the boundaries of the project, in line with the goals of Horizon Europe.

The dissemination plan will be implemented in three distinct phases, each with defined start and end dates. While the dissemination phases have specific time frames, the communication plan spans the entire project duration. However, the dissemination phases can be extended or adjusted if necessary. The aim is to maximise the impact of the project outcomes and reach a wide range of target groups, aligning with the objectives of Horizon Europe.

CONFIDENTIAL6G dissemination activities include project documentation, peer-reviewed publications, non-scientific publications and interviews, coding guidelines, source code repository, open access to research, webinars, workshops, events, conferences, and fairs.

Project documentation will describe technical outputs, APIs, architectures, models, recommendations, promotional activities, and acquired insights. These materials will be made available through project deliverables on the website and a public repository. Peer-reviewed publications will be used to ensure credibility and recognition within the scientific community.

Non-scientific publications and interviews will target a broad audience, aiming to achieve widespread awareness and validation of the project results. These publications will include articles, blog posts, position papers, and interviews tailored to end-users and the public society. Reference media platforms include CORDIS Research*EU Magazine, Telefonica Blogs, and Digital Innovation Magazine.

Coding guidelines will be provided to facilitate external development efforts, covering aspects such as development environment, security guidelines, coding style, debugging, and performance considerations. The project will also make its source code repository accessible through well-known platforms like GitHub or GitLab, encouraging other tech providers to reuse the project's outcomes.

Open access to research findings will be promoted, allowing for broader access to project results and fostering collaboration. Webinars, workshops, and events will be organized to transfer and exchange technical and socio-economic knowledge with the community. These sessions will provide hands-on training, round table discussions, mentoring, and development opportunities.

Conferences and trade fairs will be strategic mechanisms to actively interact with multiple stakeholders at a European and international level. The project will showcase its results through presentations, talks, exhibition spaces, and personal engagement in at least 30 events. Relevant events include NDSS and USENIX, TPMPC, Mobile World Congress, CPDP, GAIA-X Summit, IoT World Congress, European Cloud Summit, IoT Week, TMForum Digital Transformation World Series, and SME-oriented events (EU SME Week, 4YFN, Codemotion).

In addition, CONFIDENTIAL6G will actively participate in working groups and SDOs:

- IETF - TID is an active IETF (Internet Engineering Task Force) member and contributes to standardisation on how to build standards for cryptographic cloud storage and analysing data in a privacy-preserving way. Project will contribute to IETF Trusted Execution Environment Platforms (TEEP) and IETF Remote Attestation procedures (RATS) working groups and will promote and reflect the project's results in these forums.
- ISO SC27 JTC1, WG2 - TUE is a member of WG2 on cryptographic algorithms. TUE has been a major contributor (3 out of 6 sections) to Standing Document SD8 on post-quantum cryptography.
- ODL - Open Daylight: Telefonica has made several contributions to this open-source SDN framework and have a position at its Advisory Board.
- ETSI - TID is a Chair of the Network Operator Council (NFV ISG), founding member (NFV SEC) and participant of SAI and RIS ISG, active contributor to the TC of TC CYBER;
- OSM - Open source MANO: TID leads the initiative and is one of the main contributors
- 3GPP - TNO: participation on SA1 Requirements and SA3 Security. TID: participation on SA3 Security. NNF: participation on SA3 security.

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- O-RAN - TID: TSC/EB/WGs Members of TSC and EB; VTT: member (research contributor)
- NIST - TUE: has contributed to the NIST-PQC standardisation project with 6 systems of which 4 are currently in Round 3. TUE has also been active in public consultations and submitted public comments to several draft standards and revisions. Ed25519 and XMSS, developed by TUE, are standardised by NIST. TUG has also contributed with 2 designs to the NIST-PQC standardisation project which are currently listed as alternative candidates in Round 3.
- OSF Open-stack - ZEN is a member of the OSF Openstack Edge Computing group and will contribute to the presentation and discussion coordinated by Openstack.
- GAIA-X: VTT: member; part of Finnish GAIA-X hub and active participant in GAIA-X work groups. TNO: member, part of Dutch GAIA-X hub and active participant in GAIA-X work groups.
- OpenCORD - TID is a member of the Technical Steering Team for CORD

These activities will be bringing together community efforts to drive common discussions and strategies. The project will capitalize on consolidated activities from partners and contribute to open-source initiatives, fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange.

Overall, the dissemination strategy and plan for CONFIDENTIAL6G aims to maximise the impact of its outcomes and reach a wide range of target groups, ensuring the project's contributions are recognized and utilised beyond the project's boundaries. In Table 1, the list of the events where CONFIDENTIAL6G partners were presented is given.

Table 1. List of dissemination and communication activities

Event	Date and place	Photo/ Link	Type of contribution
ETSI Research Conference	06-08.02 2023, Sophia Antipolis, France		Presentation and poster

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<p>European Blockchain Convention</p>	<p>15-17.02.2023. Barcelona, Spain</p>		<p>Booth</p>
<p>International Conference on Advanced Research in Computing 2023</p>	<p>23-24.02.2023, Online</p>	<p>Blockchain for 5G and Beyond Networks, Link</p>	<p>Speaker slot</p>
<p>3rd webinar of the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) on the Stream B1 & B4 projects addressing: Architecture & Secure Services and Security</p>	<p>23.02.2023. Online</p>	<p>Project presentation (Slides Video)</p>	<p>Presentation</p>
<p>AI for Good, Enabling intrusion detection in 5G networks via novel datasets</p>	<p>02.03.2023, Online</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>Panel</p>
<p>CrossFyre 23 (affiliated to Eurocrypt 23)</p>	<p>23.04.2023. Lyon, France</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>Event participation</p>
<p>6G Global Summit 2023</p>	<p>03-04.05.2023. Bahrain</p>	<p><i>Panelist for Session 4: Securing the Future: Cyber Security in the 6G Era</i></p>	<p>Panel</p>

Tomorrow Conference	12-14.05.2023. Belgrade Serbia		Event participation
2023 EuCNC & 6G Summit	06-09.06.2023. Gothenburg, Sweden	Video feature (Project Coordinator)	Featured video
IFIP Networking / TC6 meeting	12.06.2023. Barcelona, Spain	Link	Meeting participation
2nd CITEA Digital Cyprus Conference 2023	22.06.2023. Cyprus	Link	Speaker
Monero Konferenco	23-26.06.2023 Praha	Link	Speaker
Blockchain for the metaverse: A Review, Future Generation Computer Systems, Volume 143, 2023, Pages 401-419, ISSN 0167-739X	Thien Huynh-The, Thippa Reddy Gadekallu, Weizheng Wang, Gokul Yenduri, Pasika Ranaweera, Quoc-Viet Pham, Daniel Benevides da Costa, Madhusanka Liyanage	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2023.02.008 .	Journal publication

3.1 EUROPEAN SMART NETWORKS AND SERVICES JOINT UNDERTAKING (SNS JU)

CONFIDENTIAL6G, a part of the European Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU), stands to gain numerous advantages in terms of communication and dissemination of project news and results. SNS JU, a Public-Private Partnership, aims to promote industrial leadership in 5G and 6G networks and services within Europe. By actively engaging with SNS JU, CONFIDENTIAL6G will leverage its social media presence, collaborate with other 6G projects, and tap into the wider ecosystem to amplify its impact and foster technological advancements.

By participating in SNS JU meetings and leveraging their social media channels, CONFIDENTIAL6G can gain increased visibility and recognition among the European and international 6G community. SNS JU brings together diverse stakeholders, providing CONFIDENTIAL6G with valuable networking opportunities to connect with other projects and organisations working on 6G technologies. CONFIDENTIAL6G can tap into the collective expertise, knowledge, and resources available within the SNS JU ecosystem, including technical reports, research findings, and best practices related to 6G networks and services.

Active engagement with SNS JU enables CONFIDENTIAL6G to establish collaborations and partnerships with other projects, industry, and research institutions, fostering joint initiatives and potential future collaborations. Furthermore, Participation in SNS JU activities allows CONFIDENTIAL6G to contribute to the development of standards, guidelines, and policy recommendations in the 6G domain, positioning the project as an influential player and shaping the future of 6G networks and services. By leveraging these benefits, CONFIDENTIAL6G can effectively promote its project, expand its ecosystem, and maximise its impact within the 6G landscape, contributing to Europe's technological sovereignty and the digital transformation of society and the economy.

A summary of activities already performed in the scope of SNS is provided below:

- Input to SNS Call assessment questionnaire Stream B - Strand D, August 2022
- Input to SNS Call assessment questionnaire, October 2022
- Contribution to the SNS Annual Journal 2023 prepared by SNS OPS, February 2023

D6.1 Plan For Dissemination And Exploitation Including Communication Activities

- Participation at the ETSI/EC/6G-IA workshop on SNS projects Standardization plans, 6-8 February 2023, ETSI HQs, Sophia-Antipolis, France
- Presentation of project at the 3rd webinar of the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) on the Stream B1 & B4 projects addressing: Architecture & Secure Services and Security, 23 February 2023
- Participation to Preparatory SNS Steering Board meetings (online) on 13 March 2023 and 12 May 2023
- Input for SNS JU Phase 1 - Projects Questionnaire, May 2023
- Participation to “Passing the Torch event: 5G-PPP to SNS JU” (online), 25 May 2023
- Project video feature recorded at the 2023 EuCNC & 6G Summit, 6-9 June 2023, Gothenburg, Sweden

4 COMMUNICATION STRATEGY AND PLAN

The communication strategy and plan for the CONFIDENTIAL6G project focus on effectively promoting the project and its results, targeting a wide audience while capitalising on the consortium's multilingual capabilities and international presence. The strategy is based on various measures to raise awareness and engage with the audience, utilising a comprehensive Promotion Mix. It also emphasises the importance of a coordinated and fully-fledged master plan to achieve the projected impact of the project.

4.1 COMMUNICATION PLAN IN CONFIDENTIAL6G

Communication activities in the CONFIDENTIAL6G will be promoting the project and its achievements to the public and build traction among the target audience and create awareness about the project's goals and outcomes. To achieve this, CONFIDENTIAL6G employs a comprehensive communication plan that leverages various channels and strategies.

The project will have a duration of 36 months and WP6 will be running since M1 until M36. All activities are carefully planned so as to achieve the proposed KPIs during the project duration. The project is focused on the development of sound and present visual identity and dissemination and communication strategy (Figure 2). The communication activities of the CONFIDENTIAL6G project will involve the implementation of campaigns throughout the project's lifetime. These campaigns will be designed to build traction among the target audience, leveraging the consortium's multilingual nature to cover a broad international footprint. The goal is

to reach out to a critical mass of stakeholders, effectively disseminating information about the project and its accomplishments.

Activity	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36		
Social media (TW, LI)	x																																					
PPT, Docs		x																																				
Website			x																																			
Flyer			x																																			
Brochures			x																																			
Poster			x																x																			
Social media (YT)						x																																
Newsletter						x			x									x			x						x				x				x			x
Videos										x										x																		
MOOC																																						
Podcast												x							x																			
Events				x		x	x	x		x					x	x			x		x		x															
Scientific publications	x	x		x					x						x	x				x		x					x				x				x			x
Webinar/ Workshop												x							x																			
Press/ Blog			x						x																													
Wiki and GitHub			x																																			

Figure 2. Gantt for the foreseen communication and dissemination activities

The project will implement various activities to promote and showcase its platform effectively. To ensure its success, the project team devised a comprehensive plan, that includes various activities to effectively promote and showcase the project outcomes. To effectively reach different target groups in CONFIDENTIAL6G, a range of communication channels has been identified. These channels are carefully selected to ensure that information is disseminated in a manner that resonates with each specific audience. From traditional channels, such as the project website, to the dynamic realm of social media, CONFIDENTIAL6G utilises a diverse array of communication channels.

A project logo, templates for deliverables, milestones, presentations, and posters are developed ensuring a consistent and professional visual identity throughout the project. The project recognized the power of email campaigns as a means of reaching out to potential stakeholders. An ambitious target of contacting at least 2000 individuals or organizations throughout the project, ensuring that the platform's value proposition reached a wide audience. In parallel, the project has launched a website by the third month. The goal was to have the website live and accessible, attracting more than 3000 unique visitors by the end of month 36. The website will serve as a central hub of information, engaging visitors and highlighting the platform's features and benefits.

To leverage the influence of social media, the project team will build a strong presence across various platforms. By the end of the project, the aim is to gather a substantial following of at least 2000 followers. The project also sets a target of

generating a monthly average of over 80 impressions, ensuring that the platform's visibility remains high throughout the project's duration.

Recognizing the importance of consistent communication, the project plans to publish a minimum of 10 newsletters, keeping subscribers informed about the project's progress, milestones, and exciting updates. Additionally, the project aims to issue at least 6 press releases to generate media coverage and create a buzz around the platform's development. Knowing the value of engaging with the developer community, the project team seeks to make a minimum of 6 unique contributions to developer communities. By actively participating in discussions, sharing insights, and providing support, they aim to establish themselves as thought leaders and attract the attention of skilled developers.

The offline promotion is also crucial for reaching a diverse audience. Project plan to distribute a minimum of 1500 hard copies of brochures, flyers, posters, and other promotional materials, ensuring that the platform's message resonates beyond the digital realm. To engage with the audience on a more dynamic level, the team plans to produce a minimum of 3 short videos. These videos will provide valuable insights, demonstrations, and tutorials related to the platform, further enhancing user understanding and interest.

Furthermore, the project team commits to publishing a minimum of 10 technical publications, including public deliverables. Project also aim to produce a project brochure and at least one white paper, providing comprehensive information and thought-provoking insights to the audience. For the scientific publications, a minimum of 10 peer-reviewed scientific items will be published in peer reviewed journals. In addition, at least 10 peer-reviewed papers at conferences will be published. For global audience and non-scientific community, the project team aims to publish at least 50 articles, blog posts, position papers, and interviews. CONFIDENTIAL6G seek to create awareness among end-users and stakeholders, effectively conveying the project message.

To ensure a streamlined development process, the team publishes at least one coding guidelines paper, providing developers with best practices and recommendations for working on the platform. To further emphasize their commitment to open access, the team aims to achieve at least 1000 downloads of their CONFIDENTIAL6G material. Project will also organise a minimum of 10

webinars and workshops, with a target of engaging at least 200 unique participants, as well as other events.

4.1.1 LOGO AND VISUAL IDENTITY

To maintain a consistent visual identity, CONFIDENTIAL6G establishes a recognizable brand presence - a unique logo and the templates that aligns with the project's visual style. The logo (Figure 3) and templates (Figure 4, Figure 5, Figure 6, Figure 7, and Figure 8) are carefully designed to reflect the project's objectives and values. They are used consistently across various communication materials, such as presentations, reports, and promotional items. This cohesive visual identity enhances brand recognition and helps establish CONFIDENTIAL6G's presence in the target audience's perception.

Figure 3. CONFIDENTIAL6G Logo

The design, brainstorming and voting procedures led to selection of the final version of the logo which are first selected from the proposed and fine-tuned until the final design.

Figure 4. CONFIDENTIAL6G Deliverable template design

Figure 5. CONFIDENTIAL6G power point presentation first page design

Figure 6. CONFIDENTIAL6G power point presentation partners' page design

Figure 7. CONFIDENTIAL6G power point presentation design

info@confidential6g.eu

Figure 8. CONFIDENTIAL6G power point presentation concluding page

CONFIDENTIAL6G acknowledges the support received from the European Union in co-funding the project. As per the guidelines set by the European Commission, communication efforts, dissemination strategies, and any significant outcomes associated with the project must recognize the EU's support. CONFIDENTIAL6G ensures that the European flag emblem and a funding statement highlighting the co-funding by the European Union are prominently displayed in relevant communication materials, including electronic brochures, presentations, posters, and other information materials.

Funding statement:

“Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

In addition to the funding statement, CONFIDENTIAL6G's website also prominently features the logo of the European Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) as presented in Figure 9 below. The SNS JU logo is displayed in accordance with the SNS JU brand book and guidelines.

Figure 9. 6G SNS banner

4.1.2 WEBSITE

The project's website presented in Figure 10 and Figure 11 serves as the primary hub for promoting CONFIDENTIAL6G activities and outcomes to all target audiences. It offers comprehensive information about the project, its objectives, the consortium, and the support received from the European Union. With a mobile-friendly design, quick loading times, and full accessibility, the website is optimized for user experience. Additionally, integration with social media platforms ensures broader visibility and engagement. The structure (Site Map) of the website is given below.

Site Map:

HOME PAGE

- Project Resume
- Project partners
- News
- Footer
- Funding acknowledgement (EU)
- SNS logo
- Social media links

ABOUT US

- About CONFIDENTIAL6G
- Objectives

WORK PACKAGES

- Project structure
- Description of work packages

USE CASES

- Use case 1
- Use case 2
- Use case 3

PARTNERS

- Members of CONFIDENTIAL6G team (resume,role in the project)
- Partner's logotypes

D6.1 Plan For Dissemination And Exploitation Including Communication Activities

- Links to partners social media and website
- NEWS
 - News about the project
- Contact US
 - Contact form

CONFIDENTIAL6G will research post-quantum cryptography (PQC) in order to create tools, libraries, SDKs and other artifacts needed for future 6G technologies

- > **Domain #1**
Confidential Computing Enablers
Confidential Computing enablers: Lattice-based cryptography for Fully Homomorphic Encryption, Secure Multi-party Computation, TEE attestation handling, collaborative AI/ML.
- > **Domain #2**
Secure Communication Enablers
Confidential Communication enablers: PQC TLS and other protocols, Blockchain-based data exchange, Zero-knowledge Proofs (ZKPs), confidential Smart Contracts, Decentralised Identifiers (DIDs) and Verifiable Credentials (VCs), and a new concept of Anonymous Credentials (AC)
- > **Domain #3**
IoT Security Enablers
Confidential Edge and IoT enablers: embedded FHE, PQC for constrained devices, large-scale networks of connected devices involved in federated learning and cryptography necessary to support this.

Figure 10. Website opening page part 1

D6.1 Plan For Dissemination And Exploitation Including Communication Activities

IN A NUTSHELL

In CONFIDENTIAL6G, our goal is to ensure secure and private computation in the cloud-edge continuum of 6G by developing modern cryptographic techniques, tools, and libraries. We recognize the importance of implementing privacy preservation and security of data in heterogeneous environments and contexts, and thus, we prioritize researching security enablers. We aim to tackle the potential danger posed by near-future quantum computers, which can break contemporary encryptions, by exploring novel cryptographic operations.

13 PARTNERS
Consortium combines the industrial expertise from industry, SMEs and academic and research excellence.

10 DIFFERENT COUNTRIES
Including Austria, Estonia, Germany, Greece, Ireland, France, Spain, Netherlands, Finland and Serbia.

5 MIL EUR
CONFIDENTIAL6G project is financed by EU Commission with the total budget of 5 mil EU.

Project Partners

We are proud to collaborate with a diverse group of project partners who share our vision and commitment to excellence.

Latest News

Website is online!

Information on 6G and 6G Advancements Now Accessible to the Public.

Confidential6G.eu Officially Releases Website to the Public

As companies and organizations around the world aim to develop the next generation of telecommunications technology, the EU-funded Confidential6G project has been making significant strides towards achieving a fully secure and trustworthy 6G network. And as of today...

[Read More >](#)

CONFIDENTIAL6G on The European Blockchain Convention

The European Blockchain Convention (EBC) held in Barcelona from FEB 8-10, 2023 and it is one of the biggest events for the blockchain industry. #CONFIDENTIAL6G was proud to have been represented by the Zentao Lab with a booth at the event. The conference provided...

[Read More >](#)

CONFIDENTIAL6G at ETSI Workshop 2023

Nokia, Zentao, University College Dublin participated at the ETSI (European Telecommunications Standards Institute) Conference, which took place in Sophia Antipolis, France, in the beginning of February 2023. The partners were invited and had a chance to present the...

[Read More >](#)

CONFIDENTIAL6G Kick-off Meeting

The CONFIDENTIAL6G Project is an exciting new collaboration that promises to improve the security of future communications. Bringing together 13 partners from 10 different countries, the project aims to develop a secure framework for 6G cloud and edge technology. The...

[Read More >](#)

Co-funded by the European Union

6G SNS

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Quick Links:

- [About](#)
- [Workpackages](#)
- [Partners](#)
- [Contact](#)

Follow Us:

Figure 11. Website opening page part 2

4.1.3. SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS

CONFIDENTIAL6G recognizes the significance of social media platforms, specifically X and LinkedIn, for enhancing its online presence and communication efforts. These platforms are strategically utilised to engage with various stakeholders and achieve specific objectives. LinkedIn is leveraged as a professional platform, allowing researchers to showcase their expertise, publications, and experience. It serves as a hub for networking, collaboration, and knowledge exchange among researchers within their fields. Researchers can expand their connections, explore collaboration opportunities, and share research insights with peers.

X, on the other hand, serves as a micro-blogging platform where researchers share research findings, promote publications, and connect with peers in a concise and timely manner. Additionally, X offers the opportunity to engage with policymakers, journalists, and the wider public, contributing to relevant discussions using hashtags.

By utilizing created LinkedIn (Figure 12) and X (Figure 13) channels, project strategically, aims to establish a strong online presence, foster collaboration, and effectively disseminate research outcomes. These platforms enable researchers to expand their networks, promote their work, and engage with diverse audiences. In an increasingly digital world, embracing social media is crucial for researchers to achieve their research objectives and have a broader impact in their respective fields. The current statistics around CONFIDENTIAL6G channels including followers, impression and posts, are presented in Table 2.

CONFIDENTIAL6G Channels:

- LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/c6g-project/>
- X https://twitter.com/C6G_eu

Table 2. CONFIDENTIAL6G current social media followers

Channel	Followers	Impressions	No of posts
	90	6655	20
	24	2591	18

Figure 12. CONFIDENTIAL6G Social media channels - LinkedIn

Figure 13. CONFIDENTIAL6G Social media channels - X

4.1.4. OTHER TOOLS AND CHANNELS

Email campaigns are a highly effective means of reaching out to end-users, key technology communities, and partners within the "Partnerships & Networks" domain. CONFIDENTIAL6G designs and executes a portfolio of email templates tailored to specific target groups, incorporating call-to-action measures to drive traffic and engagement. All email communication adheres to EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) guidelines, utilizing compliant solutions available on the market.

CONFIDENTIAL6G is committed to utilising additional communication activities to enhance the promotion of the project and its outcomes. Among these activities, newsletters assume a critical role in broadcasting essential project updates and upcoming opportunities. These newsletters serve as a valuable resource, offering a concise yet comprehensive overview of CONFIDENTIAL6G's progress, upcoming webinars, and events. By regularly distributing newsletters, the project ensures that the target audience remains well-informed and actively engaged, fostering a strong and vibrant community of stakeholders.

CONFIDENTIAL6G places significant importance on engaging with the press and wider media outlets. A joint press release is prepared early in the project to

introduce the project's ambition and its partner organisations. Moreover, CONFIDENTIAL6G benefits from corporate press releases published by consortium partners, extending the project's reach to their respective networks.

CONFIDENTIAL6G recognizes the value of engaging with developer communities to foster industry collaboration and innovation. The project will actively connect with and execute promotional activities in communities and channels associated with consortium members. These activities will leverage the expertise and networks of partners such as TUE, VTT, TID's, and IMDEA, reaching out to industry professionals and developers through platforms like X, LinkedIn, and YouTube.

Printing/Merchandising: CONFIDENTIAL6G understands the power of physical materials in creating a lasting impact at events and meetings. The project has already taken a proactive approach by designing roll-ups (Figure 14) and flyers (Figure 15) that incorporate the project's visual identity. These materials showcase a consistent and professional brand presence, reflecting the project's objectives and progress. They have been successfully utilised at conferences, effectively capturing attendees' attention and conveying key project information in a visually appealing manner. In addition to printed resources, CONFIDENTIAL6G is also exploring the use of appealing and reusable merchandising items, including T-shirts and stickers. These creative measures aim to attract a broader audience and enhance brand visibility, further reinforcing the project's presence and recognition.

D6.1 Plan For Dissemination And Exploitation Including Communication Activities

CONFIDENTIAL6G

Confidential Computing and Privacy-preserving Technologies for 6G

CONFIDENTIAL6G will develop cryptographic, quantum-resistant protocols and security proofs tools, libraries, mechanism and architectural blueprints for confidentiality in 6G.

Cryptography

Cryptographic enablers for confidential computing (FHE, S MPC, TEE) and post-quantum networking, DL1 privacy enablers (ZKP), Support for embedded edge devices and HW.

Confidential Computing

Confidentia Computing via FHE, S MPC and HW TEEs, Collaborative AI/ML, Confidentia core data, Remote Attestation, Secure enclave abstraction, Secure key distribution.

Confidential Networking

Post-quantum secure network protocols, Secure data sharing and access control, Private blockchain Smart Contracts, DIDs and VCs, Federated AI/ML, orchestration.

The main ambition of the CONFIDENTIAL6G project is to enable secure and privacy-preserving computation via novel, modern cryptographic techniques and operations across the cloud-edge continuum that will be necessary in 6G.

Prerequisite for implementation of privacy preservation and security of data in these heterogeneous environments and different contexts is robust modern cryptographic techniques, tools and libraries.

This is why it is essential to focus the research on these security enablers as well, especially with the awareness of danger that can be posed by near-future quantum computers and their capabilities to break the contemporary encryptions.

CONFIDENTIAL6G will research post-quantum cryptography (PQC) in order to create tools, libraries, SDKs and other artefacts needed for future 6G technologies

- Domain #1: Confidential Computing enablers: Lattice-based cryptography for Fully Homomorphic Encryption, Secure Multi-party Computation, TEE attestation handling, collaborative AI/ML.
- Domain #2: Confidential Communication enablers: PQC TLS and other protocols, Blockchain-based data exchange, Zero-knowledge Proofs (ZKPs), confidential Smart Contracts, Decentralised Identifiers (DIDs) and Verifiable Credentials (VCs), and a new concept of Anonymous Credentials (AC).
- Domain #3: Confidential Edge and IoT enablers: embedded FHE, PQC for constrained devices, large-scale networks of connected devices involved in federated learning and cryptography necessary to support this.

Use Case 1: Predictive maintenance for airline operations using blockchain-based data sharing platform and Federated AI/ML orchestration

The key validation: (i) confidential Smart Contracts and transactions in DL1 in order to hide information about asset metadata in the data marketplace for aviation assets (turns); (ii) blockchain enhanced access control layer that would enable verifiable logs and traces of consent, coupled with blockchain configured proxy mechanisms; (iii) secure and encrypted metadata transfer to the orchestration layer based on hypernodes, distributed between aviation companies; (iv) federated AI/ML orchestration that will ensure that computation is brought to the data sets in the edge data centers near the airports in a secure manner; (v) remote attestation and result handling for the applied algorithm for predictive maintenance.

Use Case 2: Privacy-preserving confidential computing platform that enables mitigation of internal threats for telecom cloud providers

The key validation: (i) automated handling of confidential VMs, including their creation and initialization in a programmable manner and using cloud APIs; (ii) TEE assistments to help cloud providers enable TEEs in the cloud; (iii) software framework for handling remote attestations; (iv) software management agent (SMA) for management of secure VMs and enablement of secure TLS connections with enablers; (v) confidential container framework and network support.

USE CASES

CONFIDENTIAL6G is a collaborative Research and Innovation Action project awarded by the European Commission to a consortium of 13 different partners. This funding is part of the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme under Grant Agreement No 101096435.

CONFIDENTIAL6G will develop cryptographic quantum-resistant protocols and security proofs tools, libraries, mechanism and architectural blueprints for confidentiality in 6G.

Figure 14. CONFIDENTIAL6G Rollup design

CONFIDENTIAL6G

Confidential Computing and Privacy-preserving Technologies for 6G

CONFIDENTIAL6G will develop cryptographic quantum-resistant protocols and security proofs tools, libraries, mechanism and architectural blueprints for confidentiality in 6G.

Cryptography

Cryptographic enablers for confidential computing (FHE, SMPC, TEE) and post-quantum networking, DLT privacy enablers (ZKP), Support for embedded edge devices and HW.

Confidential Computing

Confidential Computing via FHE, SMPC and HW TEEs, Collaborative AI/ML, Confidential containers, Remote attestations, Secure enclave abstractions, Secure key distributions.

Confidential Networking

Post-quantum secure network protocol, Secure data sharing and access control, Private blockchain Smart Contracts, DIDs and VCs, Federated AI/ML orchestration.

The main ambition of the CONFIDENTIAL6G project is to enable secure and privacy-preserving computation via novel, modern cryptographic techniques and operations across the cloud-edge continuum that will be necessary in 6G. Prerequisite for implementation of privacy preservation and security of data in these heterogeneous environments and different contexts is robust modern cryptographic techniques, tools and libraries. This is why it is essential to focus the research on these security enablers as well, especially with the awareness of danger that can be posed by near-future quantum computers and their capabilities to break the contemporary encryptions.

CONFIDENTIAL6G will research post-quantum cryptography (PQC) in order to create tools, libraries, SDKs and other artefacts needed for future 6G technologies:

- Domain #1:** Confidential Computing enablers: Lattice-based cryptography for Fully Homomorphic Encryption, Secure Multi-party Computation, TEE attestation handling, collaborative AI/ML
- Domain #2:** Confidential Communication enablers: PQC TLS and other protocols, Blockchain-based data exchange, Zero-knowledge Proofs (ZKPs), confidential Smart Contracts, Decentralised Identifiers (DIDs) and Verifiable Credentials (VCs), and a new concept of Anonymous Credentials (AC)
- Domain #3:** Confidential Edge and IoT enablers: embedded FHE, PQC for constrained devices, large-scale networks of connected devices involved in federated learning and cryptography necessary to support this.

Use Cases

U1 Use Case 1: Predictive maintenance for airline consortium using blockchain-based data sharing platform and federated AI/ML orchestration

U2 Use Case 2: Privacy-preserving confidential computing platform that enables mitigation of internal threats for telecom cloud providers

U3 Use Case 3: Intelligent connected vehicle, mission-critical services, OTA updates, FL/ML and vehicle to infrastructure communication

CONFIDENTIAL6G is a collaborative Research and Innovation Action project awarded by the European Commission to a consortium of 13 different partners. The funding is part of the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101096435.

Figure 15. CONFIDENTIAL6G Flyer design

Slide decks are employed as a point of entry for the project, replacing websites in certain contexts, including events, email campaigns, and one-on-one meetings. CONFIDENTIAL6G develops multiple versions of slide decks to tailor content to specific target audiences and highlight key achievements. Furthermore, CONFIDENTIAL6G produces multimedia materials, including videos and clips, to enhance communication efforts. These materials provide self-explanatory and engaging content for the website, social media platforms, and other distribution channels. Webinars and live training modules are recorded and made available to extend the impact beyond the project's duration.

5 KPIS AND PROJECT MONITORING

In this chapter, we will present the key performance indicators (KPIs) and project monitoring approach for CONFIDENTIAL6G. Main focus is to align our dissemination and communication actions with measurable targets and establish an effective monitoring system.

The success of CONFIDENTIAL6G relies on the implementation of dissemination and communication strategies. Therefore, we have identified specific KPIs for each activity to gauge progress and measure the impact of the efforts taken. Monitoring these KPIs will enable to track the effectiveness of dissemination and communication actions and make adjustments if needed.

To facilitate monitoring, partners will have access to an Excel file designed for tracking their dissemination work throughout the project's duration. This comprehensive tracking system will include various parameters, such as press coverage, contributions to specialised journals, presentations at events, and mentions by relevant target groups in public files. By regularly updating the monitoring file, we can assess our performance against the communication KPIs and ensure we are on track to achieve our objectives.

Table 3 provides an overview of the main KPIs for dissemination and communication activities in CONFIDENTIAL6G:

Table 3. CONFIDENTIAL6G Dissemination and communication KPIs

Activity	Performance Indicator
Email Campaigns	Contact points (up to the end of the project): ≥ 2000
Website	Website online by: M3; Unique Visitors from M36: $> 3,000$
Social media	Followers (by the end of the project) ≥ 2000 ; No. of impressions (monthly average): > 80
Newsletters	Number of newsletters ≥ 10 ;
Press Releases	Number of press releases ≥ 6 ;
Developer Community	Target Values: Unique Contributions to Developer Communities: ≥ 6
Printing / Merchandising	Target Values: No. of hard copies (i.e., brochures, flyers,

	posters, etc.) distributed ≥ 1500
Slide Decks	Target Values: No. of slide decks shared ≥ 6
Multimedia Material	Target Values: No. of short videos produced (in total): ≥ 3
Logo & Templates	Target Values: Project logo: 1; Templates (deliverables, milestones, presentations, posters) : ≥ 4
Project Documentation	Technical publications (including public deliverables: ≥ 10 ; Project brochure: 1 White paper: ≥ 1
Peer-reviewed Publications	Peer-reviewed scientific items in journals ≥ 10 ; Peer-reviewed papers in conferences ≥ 10 .
Non-scientific Publications and interviews	Publications in articles, blog posts, position papers, interviews, and any other non-scientific publication oriented end-users ≥ 50 .
Coding Guidelines	Coding guidelines paper ≥ 1
Source Code Repository	Source code published in ≥ 2 different repositories
Open Access to Research	Downloads of CONFIDENTIAL6G material ≥ 1000 ; Online repository: 1; Openly available publications ≥ 15 ; Openly available datasets ≥ 3 ;
Webinars/ Workshops/ Events	Target values: Webinars and workshops ≥ 10 ; Unique participants to webinars and workshops ≥ 200
Conferences/ Fairs	Target Values: Fairs to Participate: ≥ 3
Working Groups	Target Values: Participation to Working Groups: ≥ 2

6 EXPLOITATION STRATEGY AND PLAN

Maximising the potential of valuable results and findings is essential for effective exploitation, practical applications, and achieving commercial success. Our exploitation strategy aims to fully leverage the outcomes of our project by adopting a comprehensive and systematic approach that covers various aspects.

While CONFIDENTIAL6G focuses on disruptive research and targets innovations at relatively low Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) during the project, it acknowledges that the proposed solutions are still distant from market introduction. Nonetheless, the CONFIDENTIAL6G consortium has initiated the development of a preliminary Business Plan to guide the future commercialization of the project's outcomes in the medium to long term. At this stage, the plan is an initial approach, with the detailed version to be refined throughout the project activities.

The initial approach encompasses two key elements: a community and user sharing edition of the CONFIDENTIAL6G framework, partially open source, and the provision of professional services for a fee. Embracing open-source policies, the CONFIDENTIAL6G consortium has adopted a dual-licensing approach to effectively manage internal knowledge while also sharing specific knowledge with the scientific community. Consequently, the indicative business plan is structured around two core business axes: (a) professional-oriented services supported by the CONFIDENTIAL6G core framework and (b) audience-centric services facilitating the generation and sharing of new tools and experiences.

Table 4 outlines an indicative Business Model Canvas, which serves as an ongoing, systematic process for reporting and monitoring business steps. It allows for iterative evolution until CONFIDENTIAL6G achieves a certain level of market outreach maturity. The value of this canvas lies in its role as a dynamic observatory and scoreboard for the business plan. Regular updates will track the progress and alignment of the business potential. Since developing a comprehensive business model description necessitates in-depth knowledge of various business parameters, stakeholders, customers, and technical aspects, the consortium partners will collaboratively undertake this task. The involvement of external entities and the broader ecosystem will be vital in creating a complete business model description.

Table 4. Business Model Canvas

Indicative Business Model Canvas				
<p>Key partners</p> <p>Telco providers, Cloud providers, Critical ICT infrastructures; academia, ICT vendors and asset providers; open-source communities; standardization organizations; investors; early adopters and promoters.</p>	<p>Key activities</p> <p>Design and development of cybersecurity risk management and services; business model development for new services; maintenance and integration.</p>	<p>Value proposition</p> <p>Framework for enhancing cyber security, privacy and data protection of complex ICT infrastructures;</p> <p>Secure and robust cloud and edge infrastructure, network layer resilience to attacks; data privacy and advanced federated processing operations,</p>	<p>Customer relationship</p> <p>Long term support and future upgrades; training support; community support; dedicated assistance.</p>	<p>Customer segment</p> <p>Telco providers; Cloud providers, Professionals; Public authorities; executives and managers of service providers; third party developers; CERTs/CSIRTs; cybersecurity educational providers and training firms; cybersecurity researchers.</p>
<p>Key resources</p> <p>Scientific and research results from the project activities; successful validation of use cases.</p>			<p>Channels</p> <p>Website, social media; demonstration & dissemination activities; standardization, open source; clustering; fairs and events.</p>	
<p>Cost structure</p> <p>R&D costs; infrastructure costs (i.e. platform hosting); data centre operations; integration costs; marketing costs & ads; customer support.</p>			<p>Revenue streams</p> <p>Open source versus closed system services (licensing); tools on demand (API); direct platform sales; after-sales service; engineering services; consulting services; development contracts</p>	

CONFIDENTIAL6G recognises three main exploitation models for the project results: 1) the commercial exploitation model, which implies the paid provision of the project results to the end users, complying with a licensing scheme which will be defined at a later stage, 2) the research exploitation model, which implies the use of the research know-how acquired in future research activities, and 3) the

technological exploitation model, which implies the use of the technological know-how gained for the development of innovative products and the provision of advanced services built on top of them. CONFIDENTIAL6G will use a custom designed template in order to characterise key exploitable results, both on individual partner level and joint level. Different versions of the template will be created depending on the exploitation model which will be used. In the exploitation plan

CONFIDENTIAL6G identifies main target groups' categories that may be interested in the commercialisation of the project results: Telecom operators, Service providers, Digital Technology developers, Partnerships, Policymakers, Academia.

The **actual exploitation plan** (Figure 16) has been elaborated and will be frequently updated, aiming at maximising the exploitation levels of the project, from the involved target groups. It includes the following **four phases**:

1. **Discovery Phase:** Gathering market insights and defining business requirements while shaping the project's value proposition.
2. **Strategy Phase:** Developing the business model and analysing the competitive landscape to define the project's positioning and market entry strategy.
3. **Partnership Phase:** Creating a comprehensive business plan and securing partner buy-in to ensure collaboration and alignment with the project's goals.
4. **Validation and Commercialization Phase:** Validating the requirements, finalizing the go-to-market strategy, and establishing a long-term sustainable framework for potential commercialization of the project's offerings.

Figure 16. Exploitation plan

7 KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

In CONFIDENTIAL6G we have already identified preliminary key exploitable outcomes. As the project progresses, the detailed plan for utilising these outcomes will be developed gradually based on the intentions of our various partners. This plan will encompass the regular definition of exploitable outcomes, including technical results, methodologies, and knowledge generated by the project. These key exploitable outcomes will be evaluated based on their current stage of development, potential impact, differentiation from existing concepts or products, and other relevant factors. Ultimately, at the project's conclusion, we will produce a comprehensive roadmap for exploiting these outcomes (D6.3).

Here is a summary of the initial collective key exploitable outcomes, which will undergo further refinement and development during the project:

- Valuable Outcome #1: Confidential Toolkit
- Valuable Outcome #2: Confidential Computing
- Valuable Outcome #3: Confidential Networking
- Proof of concept for Use Case 1: Implementation of predictive maintenance for an airline consortium using a blockchain-based data sharing platform and federated AI/ML orchestration
- Proof of concept for Use Case 2: Privacy-preserving confidential computing platform enabling the mitigation of internal threats for telecom cloud providers
- Proof of concept for Use Case 3: Intelligent connected vehicle with mission-critical services, OTA updates, federated learning/artificial intelligence, and vehicle-to-infrastructure communication.

These key exploitable outcomes will be approached with different exploitation strategies from each partner participating in creation of the current key exploitable result.

The detailed exploitation plan will be based on the intentions of the different partners and will be developed progressively during the course of the project by defining at regular times the exploitable results (technical results as well as methodologies and knowledge) of the project. Key exploitable results will be assessed in terms of development status, aspects that facilitate the assessment of the potential impact, differences from existing competing concepts, products or services, etc. The final outcome will be an exploitation roadmap at the end of the

project (D6.3). The following table summarises the initial key exploitable results that will be refined during the project.

7.1 INDIVIDUAL EXPLOITATION

In this section of the deliverable the individual exploitation plans are presented. The specific strategies and actions are described to address the unique needs and objectives of different stakeholders, partners solution, or its alignment with the organisation mission and development goals. These exploitation plans aim to leverage the transparency and communication capabilities enabled by CONFIDENTIAL6G technologies to drive sustainable practices, enhance trust, and foster collaboration within the industry. By implementing these individual exploitation plans, we can ensure that the project's benefits are effectively harnessed and contribute to long-term positive change in the mining sector.

WINGS develops and delivers solutions (hardware and software) for verticals, related to: a. the Environment, b. Utilities and Infrastructures, c. Production and Manufacturing and d. Service sectors. In the four identified areas, WINGS develops seven (7) products, has launched two (2) spin-out companies and also develops one (1) product that is jointly owned with other companies. All the solutions rely on the following four main pillars: a. Devices. This is centred around IoT (Internet of Things), b. Core platform. This area is centred around 5G and other wireless technologies, edge/cloud, big data platforms, c. Applications. This is powered by AI (Artificial Intelligence) mechanisms d. Visualization, and e. Human in the Loop technologies. WINGS will exploit the outcomes of the project, towards enhancing the company's software solutions so as to extend the supported set of connectivity options and to be able to offer services with enhanced security, privacy and trust. WINGS will pursue valuable synergies with vendors and operators, to set up a collaborative infrastructure that will enable the delivery of the key exploitable outcomes.

NNF Nokia Networks France (formerly Alcatel-Lucent International) is a trusted partner for critical networks and is committed to innovation and technology leadership across mobile, fixed and cloud networks. NNF's new software solution, called Nokia Data Marketplace (NDM), is a platform for secure data sharing, using innovative technologies like blockchain to assure various aspects of security and data integrity. On the top of this solution, NNF added Federated AI/ML orchestration, aiming to achieve confidential multi-party computations in the future.

NNF will leverage on CONFIDENTIAL6G in several aspects: (i) to improve security and confidentiality of the blockchain network behind the NDM product, using ZKPs and FHE for confidential Smart Contracts; (ii) to improve network security using quantum-safe network protocols, like quantum-safe TLS; (iii) to further develop Federated AI/ML features, adding confidential container orchestration with Kubernetes support; (iv) to further enhance and secure access control mechanisms in distributed networks. Finally, NNF will leverage on standards and architectural blueprints created in CONFIDENTIAL6G to align further development and make it interoperable with other security components and other partners and vendors.

NOK Nokia Bell Labs (part of Nokia corporation) for nearly 100 years, has been inventing the future of technology, from the early days of the Bell Telephone System to the latest 5G standards. In the CONFIDENTIAL6G framework, Nokia Bell Labs will benefit in several aspects such as: (i) improve our security capabilities and research footprint on privacy preserving technologies (ii) improve our understanding of the applicability and feasibility of privacy preserving technologies in realistic use-cases of commercial interest for Nokia (iii) prepare for the upcoming changes in the cryptographic domain with the introduction of post-quantum algorithms (iv) enhance our cryptographic agility by gaining solid understanding on the post-quantum TLS design principles and thus help us prepare better our product development lifecycle to accommodate post-quantum TLS.

TID: Telefonica is one of the largest telco providers, operating in 14 countries and serving more than 300 million end-user subscribers, more than 5.5M B2B corporate customers of all sizes. Its latest focus is in 4 principal countries (Spain, Germany, UK and Brazil), in which Telefonica constantly releases new products and services, including AURA (built on the novel data strategy called "4th Platform"), LUCA and Living Apps. Telefonica envisions that through the CONFIDENTIAL6G project, and its various scalable, privacy-preserving, secured methods, modules and toolkits built within the different components, will be able to improve existing services as well as offer new ones in both B2C and B2B manner, improving compliance with GDPR and related regulation, as well as go beyond mere compliance by offering even stronger privacy guarantees to all kind of users, from single individuals to large corporate customers involved in complex ML model training. In fact, such ML computation technologies developed within CONFIDENTIAL6G, will be easily applicable to Telefonica's B2B Services such as the Living Apps (which can support internal Telefonica Apps or external 3rd-party services), as well as the Smart Steps

service from the LUCA platform. Also, FL models built with a privacy-preserving fashion could be traded or shared across borders and 3rd-party companies (e.g., other telcos, advertisers, etc.) via the Living Apps and the 4th Platform strategic effort of Telefonica. In particular, Telefonica has more than 300 B2B partners that it collaborates with for different proof of concept technological projects and demonstrations coming out of Telefonica's innovation funnels and other business units. Telefonica's LUCA, with its AI-powered decisions platform, has helped more than 75 companies and other organisations in different sectors such as retail, tourism, utilities, public administration, banking, transport, energy, etc., to deploy successful marketing, business and other corporate strategies. In addition, Telefonica invests a lot in business development, marketing and sales, and participates in the largest industrial events such as Mobile World Congress of GSMA, to promote its new products and services across the globe. The various attack detection and mitigation components can be exploited by the telco's IT and security departments to identify incidents of data leakages and attacks monitoring network traffic and enhancing anomaly detection models and techniques. Finally, being part of such a large telecom operator, TID is especially interested in the novel edge/cloud data services built within CONFIDENTIAL6G, and how they could be applicable in both fixed and mobile environments, transferring results to the ElevenPaths business unit focused on cybersecurity B2B services. The work done within the project can provide guidelines for edge/cloud network planning, orchestration and design, as well as to understand trade-offs between resource and QoE for CONFIDENTIAL6G.

VTT is a research and technology organization whose main mission is to provide research and development, technology and innovation services to the Finnish government and to domestic as well as international companies. The challenges related to cybersecurity, security of 6G and AI are among our research and development target to secure society's functions. The project provides beyond-state-of-the-art results that can be used to facilitate easy adoption of 6G for our industrial and other partners requiring customised security. These results will be passed to domestic and international clients of VTT in order to help them create reliable, robust, and cyber secure 6G solutions and applications. In addition to that, the results will strengthen VTT's expertise related to application of novel platform security technologies towards the next generation of telecommunications and cloud services.

TUE is a public university that is dedicated to excellence in research. This research is expressed through top-quality, publicly available research contributions. In the area of cryptography, the university has strong expertise in the area of post-quantum cryptography and network protocols. This project will further add to this body of expertise and the results of this project will contribute to publications in top venues that will help the university to advance research in the cryptographic research community in a highly visible area. The results will also contribute to the education at TUE, which provides a 2-year master program in cybersecurity with several courses dedicated to cryptography, including post-quantum cryptography and cryptographic protocols, as well as network security. Including cutting-edge results in education helps attract good students and ratings. The project will directly involve the training of a PhD student in cryptography in an area that is immensely important for our digital society. Regarding exploitation of technical results, TUE will not take out patents on any inventions produced during this project and instead will make all research available free and open in order to maximise chance of adoption and standardization. Code produced will be licensed in an open way (public domain or CC0). For previous results, this approach has led to adoption by IETF and NIST as well as major industry players (Apple, Cloudflare, Google, WhatsApp) and inclusion in browsers, thus contributing to better security.

UVC is an SME oriented towards confidential computing and new paradigms of protecting data “in use” and their applications in the telecom, cloud and AI/ML domains. UVC is extensively working on cocos.ai platform, a confidential multi-party computation platform for training and using AI/ML algorithms on combined data sets from mutually distrusting parties. Over the years of development UVC faced a number of still unsolved challenges - specially handling of remote attestations and confidential containers. Their support in Kubernetes is still in the early phases. UVC plans to exploit these improvements from CONFIDENTIAL6G project, but also to leverage on research that will be executed in the domain of Federated AI/ML. That way the distributed feature can be added to the cocos.ai product. Additionally, optimized FHE and SMPC schemes developed in CONFIDENTIAL6G will be used to replace hardware-dependent component for use-cases where they can present a viable option. TEE abstractions are still immature, and UVC expects to develop a secure Software Management Agent (SMA) throughout the CONFIDENTIAL6G project. This SMA would be capable to accept secure TLS traffic and schedule AI/ML workloads within the secure enclave.

Because of this, CONFIDENTIAL6G secure quantum-safe TLS will be used as the feature where opening TLS channels in the secure enclaves (TEEs) is needed.

ZEN is an SME that operates in different verticals, with commercial solutions for Web 3.0, IoT and DLT. ZEN will exploit the knowledge gained in CONFIDENTIAL6G and integrate the resulting components and modules into the company's existing solution. Most specifically, DID, DLT and Federated AI/ML will be deployed in the Gateway based service for IoT device management and operations. The service will be extended and offered to existing clients, as an upgraded service with licence including new features, as well as next client and markets that we want to target. Additional selling point will be the accommodation and fine-tuning of Zentrix's Blockchain framework with integrated Self-sovereign identity Bridge, Verifiable Credentials, and Audit Stream, which will be enriched with Federated learning capabilities and Anonymous Credentials based on ZKP.

TNO is a non-profit applied research organisation whose mission is to improve and accelerate innovation in society and industry. Specifically in mobile network technology and cryptography, TNO's departments Networks and Applied Cryptography & Quantum Algorithms will contribute in CONFIDENTIAL6G. The department of Networks consists of 60+ people with strong expertise in the field of 5G and 6G, including 3GPP standardisation. The department of Applied Cryptography & Quantum Algorithms consists of 30+ people that are specialised in SMPC, homomorphic encryption, ZKPs and post-quantum cryptography. TNO has a unique position in the Netherlands to bridge the gap between purely academic research, and the use and development of new technology in real-world applications. TNO's MPC lab is used for publishing and promoting the use of Confidential Computing technologies such as SMPC and (F)HE, with the goal to increase source code quality, improve national and international collaboration and to stimulate adoption. The results of CONFIDENTIAL6G will contribute to standardisation bodies such as ISO (for MPC) and 3GPP (for 6G), as well as publications in top venues that will further strengthen the TNO's position within both the cryptographic and the mobile networking research community.

IMD is a non-profit research institute whose mission is to do academic research of excellence in computer science and more precisely in areas whose goal is to improve the reliability and security of software. In the area of cryptography, the institute has strong expertise in the topics of secure multiparty computation, homomorphic encryption and zero knowledge proofs, among others. The results of this project will contribute to publications in top venues that will further strengthen

the institute's position within the cryptographic research community. Moreover, while the main focus of the institute is academic research, it also has frequent collaboration with industry in areas including security and cryptography. This includes recent collaboration with Spanish companies on their development of secure multi-party computation platforms for machine learning applications. The research carried out on this project, as well as the collaboration with the partners, will increase the expertise of the institute in this particular area and its ability to transfer their knowledge to industrial applications, and this will translate into improving existing collaborations with industry and likely establishing new ones. Training of junior researchers will also be an important outcome of the project. Former Ph.D. students and postdoctoral researchers in the institute work currently for telecommunication companies, research labs, especially in the sector of blockchain, and strong academic institutions, which in addition to transferring key technical knowledge to those institutions, provide important research and industrial collaborations for IMDEA. Training as a consequence of this project will reinforce this situation.

TUG: Graz University of Technology (TUG) is the second largest research and education facility for technical sciences in Austria and focuses on high-quality basic research as well as application-oriented research and industrial implementation. The Institute of Applied Information Processing and Communications (IAIK) has been active in the field of security and privacy for more than 30 years and is one of the leading research institutions in cybersecurity. Cryptographers of the institute have contributed to major worldwide competitions in cryptography (like AES, SHA-3, and CAESAR) and have strong expertise in the area of new quantum-safe cryptosystems (e.g. SPHINCS+ and Picnic) or modern privacy-preserving technologies like homomorphic encryption (e.g. Rasta), secure multiparty computation (e.g. LowMC and MiMC), zero-knowledge proof systems (Poseidon and Starkad), or the first solution for mobile private contact discovery practical for millions of users. This project fits perfectly to the expertise of the institute and will foster its strategic goals as well as strengthen its international standing and visibility. The results of this project will help to advance cryptographic research and contribute to publications in top conferences and journals. Regarding exploitation of technical results within this project, TUG will focus on open-access for all involved publications and developed software (public domain or CC0). The results will also contribute to the education at TUG and the research outcomes will be used to train and educate the next generation of scientists.

UCD: UCD participation in the CONFIDENTIAL6G project will strengthen its research and technical expertise on network security in future networks, Machine Learning and blockchain areas. UCD is also keen to strengthen its ties within the consortium and the relevant technological sectors, fostering future collaborations with top-level academic and industrial partners. As an academic institution, UCD is aiming to enrich its teaching activities at different levels (i.e., Bachelor, Master, PhD, life-long-learning) with respect to network security topics related to future networks, Machine Learning and blockchain areas. This objective will be implemented through two complementary strategies: i) channeling the technological knowledge of CONFIDENTIAL6G to the teaching program and exposing students to real-world problems tackled by the project; ii) incorporating the students in the project and giving them the opportunity to carry out state-of-the-art research activities for preparing them to the industrial sectors. Moreover, the project's results will also be used to reinforce the research activities carried out by the university. This will be implemented through: i) incorporating CONFIDENTIAL6G results to the knowledge base of researchers; ii) using the outcomes of the project to strengthen current research initiatives; iii) exploiting the project results as a catalyst for generating further research projects.

FAU: The Friedrich-Alexander-University Erlangen-Nürnberg was founded in 1743, and it is the second-largest university in Bavaria, with almost 40.000 students. Reuters ranked FAU as the 2nd most innovative university in Europe and 1st in Germany. IT security and cryptography are one of the key areas in the field of computer science. The German Research Foundation supports this area with a dedicated Research Training Group (GTG) in the area of cybercrime, which is an interdisciplinary center between IT Security, Cryptography, and Law. The results of our research are constantly published at the leading venues in IT Security, such as ACM CCS, USENIX Security, and CRYPTO. This project will further sharpen the profile of the CS department and the FAU in general. The results will influence the classes in IT Security and Cryptography in terms of education. Furthermore, all results of this project will be made publicly available, and no patents will be generated.

7.2 CONFIDENTIAL TOOLKIT

Confidential toolkit is a set of cryptographic or enablement libraries, SDKs and tools that implement cryptographic primitives, protocols and APIs for confidential computing and confidential networking. These cover Trusted Execution

Environment (TEE), Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE), Secure Multi-party Computation (SMPC), Zero-knowledge Proofs (ZKP), DLT and TLS PQC (post-quantum cryptography) and other enablers. The exploitation strategy is provided for each organisation in Table 5 below.

Target Group(s): Telecom operators, Service providers, Digital Technology developers, Partnerships, Policymakers, Society.

Table 5. Exploitation plan and strategy: KER Secure toolkit

Leading partner / Exploitation Asset	Exploitation Strategy
IMDEA: Technological transfer as a result of PhD. Training	The Ph.D. training program will leverage the project results to allow transferring the acquired knowledge to the industry, in sectors such as blockchain and telecommunications. Former Ph. D. students at IMDEA, with expertise in cryptography, are currently employed by companies related to applications of blockchain, such as Protocol Labs, Nomadic Labs and O(1) Labs, and previously by telecommunication companies such as NTT.
NNF: Improvement of NDM DLT confidentiality	NNF's product NDM uses private permissioned blockchain network as a basis of a data exchange platform and leverages on DLT characteristic of transaction immutability to implement secure logging and data monetization. Improved privacy-preserving cryptographic protocols and schemes - notably ZKP and FHE - will help further improve NDM blockchain and enhance the product.
NOK: Enablement of privacy preserving technologies in industrial environments	NOKIA will investigate the state-of-the-art libraries for homomorphic encryption under the prism of industrial applications and relevant algorithms. Based on the conducted analysis NOKIA will obtain a solid understanding of the libraries' capabilities and application domains and define a toolkit that can be exploited for further research and for commercial applications.

<p>UVC: TEE enablement procedures</p>	<p>UVC will use TEE-handling libraries, cryptographic and other enablers in order to initialize and configure TEE hardware, which is in the base of UVC’s product cocos.ai. UVC is working on development of the toolkit that includes scripts, executables, and configuration files that will result in a wizard tool that makes process of provisioning process bootstrapping of hardware with TEEs straightforward and unified across different TEE providers.</p>
<p>TID: Distributed, Private, Scalable, Hierarchical FL as a Service</p>	<p>A service (or collection of modules that can be offered as a service) that will enable third-party companies to collaborate and build ML models using the FL paradigm, in a secured, privacy-preserving fashion, using hierarchical and scalable infrastructure of edge and end-user devices, and with a distributed aggregator for scalability and fault tolerance. In 2020-2021, TID filed three patents on the topic of privacy-preserving ML, and in particular, one patent for FL as a Service, one patent for privacy-preserving FL, and a third one on FL with hierarchical DP with hierarchical FL. TID aims to explore further the technologies built within CONFIDENTIAL6G project and how they could be used within on-going services and products of Telefonica.</p>
<p>TNO: Technology transfer to society and industry</p>	<p>TNO has a set of published repositories, the so-called TNO MPC lab, with state-of-the-art Multi-Party Computation building blocks. TNO’s MPC lab has many different technologies developed in this toolkit, such as (distributed) homomorphic encryption and MPC by secret sharing. TNO will publish the developed source code for distributed post-quantum fully homomorphic encryption to</p>

	<p>increase adoption by society and industry. The uptake of solutions will be increased by dissemination activities such as a workshop and a blog and engaging with the cryptography community within and outside of the CONFIDENTIAL6G consortium.</p>
<p>TUE: Technology transfer to students and industry</p>	<p>TUE will use the project's results in its education, training the next generation of engineers and researchers on cutting-edge results for privacy and confidentiality. Prior results from TUE have been widely adopted by industry and included in standards; the key to this success is strong results filling a gap, efficient open-source implementations, and wide dissemination to the general developer community. TUE sees the Confidential Toolkit fill a similar need and will contribute its experience to ensuring wide-spread adoption.</p>
<p>VTT: 5G-test network with confidentiality services</p>	<p>VTT's test network laboratory for 5G networks and beyond, which is part of 5G Test Network Finland cooperation, will be enhanced with the trust and security related concepts developed in the project. The laboratory provides an environment to innovate, prototype and test products for future convergent communication infrastructure.</p>
<p>TUG: Technology transfer to students and industry</p>	<p>As a public university TUG will exploit the project's result in training new researchers and engineers in privacy enhancing technologies, such as FHE and MPC. TUG also intends to use the Confidential Toolkit in its effort to research cryptography and publish results at top venues.</p>

7.3 CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING

Confidential computing is a breakthrough technology that allows to encrypt data in use - while it is being processed. It is often a combination of techniques that leverages on HW-supported TEEs or SW cryptographic enablers like FHE and SMPC. However, these techniques are new, and they build upon cryptographic enablers, a set of more complex components and frameworks, building up the abstraction levels and solution definitions to the very sophisticated applications - like collaborative confidential multi-party AI/ML. The exploitation strategy is provided for each organisation in Table 6 below.

Target Group(s): Telecom operators, Service providers, Digital Technology developers, Partnerships, Policymakers, Society.

Table 6. Exploitation plan and strategy: KER Confidential Computing

Leading partner / Exploitation Asset	Exploitation Strategy
<p>NNF: Edge node AI algorithm protection</p>	<p>NNF will be leveraging TEE-based and enabled edge nodes in order to protect algorithm IPR sent to the node via distributed orchestration. AI/ML algorithms can be of very high value, and often they need to be trained or executed on the data sets that do not belong necessary to a given organization, and in the edge environments that are not completely in the control of algorithm owners. TEE and FHE-enabled computation nodes will provide sandboxes that will protect algorithms, or/and will enable execution of a code in the encrypted form (algorithm is never shown in the plain text).</p>
<p>NOK: Evaluation of privacy preserving technologies in industrial environments</p>	<p>NOKIA will research industrial use-cases (e.g., predictive maintenance) as evaluation scenarios for FHE technologies and help assess their limitations and practicability as a function of the desired functionality, data size, accuracy of predictions, etc. As such, NOKIA will be in position to evaluate better the technological and</p>

	<p>business merits of this technology.</p>
<p>UVC: TEE-based secure multi-party computing</p>	<p>UVC’s new product cocos.ai uses TEEs to achieve secure multi-party computing. However, there are a lot of challenges regarding security guarantees that the platform provides, and also regarding the implementation of the platform itself. Scheduling of the AI/ML workloads is one example of these challenges, which UVC wants to mitigate using the results obtained in CONFIDENTIAL6G. An open-source software management agent (SMA) that runs within the enclave should be capable to execute this task, while having a minimal code trust base and thus minimal attack vectors. Additionally, this SMA should be capable of fetching and decrypting data sets in protected RAM in a reliable manner. Finally, remote attestation handling frameworks should be the outcome of CONFIDENTIAL6G which will be directly used in UVC’s platform.</p>
<p>TNO: Technology transfer to society and industry</p>	<p>TNO has a set of published repositories, the so-called TNO MPC lab, with state-of-the-art Multi-Party Computation building blocks. TNO’s MPC lab addresses many different technologies for Confidential Computing developed in this toolkit, such as homomorphic encryption and MPC by secret sharing. The results of this project will contribute to the knowledge and implementation repository in the MPC lab and increase the adoption of verifiable computations. In the 3GPP standardisation process it is expected that the 6G studies will be addressed from Release 20 (end 2023) and onwards. This project will contribute to the discussions in the 3GPP SA1 requirements group and the 3GPP SA3 security group. The results of the Confidential Computing</p>

	can be used in the ISO standardisation process for Multi-Party Computation in which TNO takes part.
WINGS: Federated AI/ML	WINGS will exploit CONFIDENTIAL 6G results on federated AI/ML for confidential computing in the scope of its diverse solutions especially those applied to sensitive domains (e.g. WINGS STARLIT for remote health monitoring, WINGS ARTEMIS for utilities and infrastructures, etc).
IMDEA: Technology transfer	The new results obtained by IMDEA in this project will be published at the main conferences in the area of cryptography and reinforce its strong position in the cryptographic research community. Moreover, IMDEA Software has been assisting local industrial partners in their ongoing development and application of secure multi-party computation platforms for machine learning applications, mainly in the sector of health. The new tools developed in this project, including the collaboration with other partners with different backgrounds, will increase the expertise of the institute in this particular area and its ability to transfer their knowledge to industrial applications, which will improve existing collaborations with industry and likely help with establishing new ones.
VTT: Supporting critical application providers	VTT will transfer the developed confidential computing technologies to its customers and partners within society and industry, critical infrastructure, and telecommunication domain. Solutions suitable for different IoT, edge, and cloud platforms will enable our partners to increase security and privacy as well as protect various 6G applications and use cases.

7.4 CONFIDENTIAL NETWORKING

Confidential networking KER focuses on secure cloud-edge communication and orchestration layer. A very important aspect is further securing TLS and other networking protocols by adding quantum-safe characteristics and ensuring that those implementations are suitable for constrained edge devices as well. Blockchain networking layer will be enhanced in the domain of confidentiality and privacy preservation with ZKPs and FHE-enhanced Smart Contracts, and these SW components will be available for exploitation. Finally, a strong focus is on confidential containers, their support in Kubernetes and Federated AI/ML orchestration - which permits that data stays at the edge and is never moved (rather algorithms are moved towards the data but are protected with encryption and other confidential mechanisms). The exploitation strategy is provided for each organisation in the Table 7 below.

Target Group(s): Telecom operators, Service providers, Digital Technology developers, Partnerships, Policymakers, Society.

Table 7. Exploitation plan and strategy: KER Confidential Networking

Leading partner / Exploitation Asset	Exploitation Strategy
<p>NNF: Federated AI/ML orchestration on the top of data marketplace</p>	<p>NNF implemented a secure data exchange platform with distributed access control. Optional monetization feature is based on the underlying blockchain transactions. Top layer exposes Open APIs for programmable operations. Because of those features, this platform is suitable for running more complex applications on top, and the customers demanded feature of deploying AI/ML algorithms that can utilise data sets exchanged (or bought and sold) through the platform. For this reason, NNF will exploit CONFIDENTIAL6G results in the domain of confidential Federated AI/ML orchestration, which will permit sending algorithms to the edge and applying them there through blockchain-configured distributed proxy data access control, while keeping algorithm IPR protected.</p>
<p>UVC: Confidential containers orchestration</p>	<p>While building platform for collaborative confidential AI/ML, UVC faced the challenge of so</p>

	<p>called Confidential Containers, a new paradigm that represents adapting of classical Linux containers, Kubernetes CRI and containerization standards like Containerd to use Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) and their accompanying mechanisms like remote attestations. By exploiting those results from CONFIDENTIAL6G, UVC will completely enable Kubernetes-orchestrated confidential computing, deployed and automated via confidential containers, and this will be a very competitive feature in UVC's cocos.ai platform.</p>
<p>WINGS: Federated AI/ML</p>	<p>WINGS will exploit CONFIDENTIAL6G results on federated AI/ML for confidential communication in the scope of its diverse solutions especially those applied to sensitive domains (e.g. WINGS STARLIT for remote health monitoring, WINGS ARTEMIS for utilities and infrastructures, etc).</p>
<p>TUE: Technology transfer via education and to industry</p>	<p>TUE will integrate the results from CONFIDENTIAL6G into its curriculum at the masters and PhD level. Students will be trained on post-quantum cryptography, secure networking protocols, and privacy enhancing technologies such as HFE, MPC, and ZK proofs. TUEs prior research has been standardized by the CFRG and NIST and is available in browsers and operating systems. TUE will leverage this prior success and contacts to ensure wide-spread adoption of the project's results.</p>
<p>UCD: Technological transfer via Ph.D. training</p>	<p>UCD will perform research and development related to blockchain and federated learning domains. The institute will conduct a well-established and structured Ph.D. training program to transfer the project's results to industrial domains of blockchain and telecommunications. UCD already has a set of Ph.D. courses focusing on cryptography, machine learning, and blockchain. The outcomes of this project will enhance the delivery of these</p>

	courses while UCD collaboration with the European industries via existing SFI (Science Foundation Ireland) research centers CONNECT (Focus is beyond 5G), Insight (Focus is ML), and ML-Labs (Focus is ML Ph.D. training) will significantly improve through dissemination.
TUG: Technology transfer to students and industry	TUG educates masters and PhD students in the area of cryptography and information security. Thus TUG will include the results of the project into its curriculum, to train a new generation of students on the state-of-the-art in FHE, MPC and ZK-proofs.
FAU: Technology transfer via education and to Industry	FAU will utilise the results in the training program for master's and Ph.D. students in secure multi-party computation, outsourced computation, and cryptocurrencies (in particular in the area of theory and practice of blockchains).

7.5 USE CASE 1: PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE FOR AIRLINE

Use case 1 is producing application of predictive maintenance in aviation. It demonstrates confidential multi-party AI/ML computation and federated AI/ML orchestration, and verifies techniques produced in WP2, WP3 and WP4, producing practical building blocks for industrial use cases in different verticals. The exploitation strategy is provided for each organisation in the Table 8 below.

Target Group(s): Telecom operators, Service providers, Digital Technology developers.

Table 8. Exploitation plan and strategy: KER Proof of concept for Use case 1: Predictive maintenance for airline consortium using blockchain-based data sharing platform and federated AI/ML orchestration

Leading partner / Exploitation Asset	Exploitation Strategy
NNF: Predictive maintenance in aviation use case	NNF created NDM (Nokia Data Marketplace) product for secure data exchange. For the commercial needs, NNF is preparing use cases that are demonstrated to the customers.

	CONFIDENTIAL6G use case #1 will demonstrate predictive maintenance capabilities but will also enhance features of confidential federated AI/ML orchestration that NNF will reuse in commercial context.
NOK: Predictive maintenance and secure KPI calculation in industrial networks	NOKIA will exploit the learnings from CONFIDENTIAL6G use-case #1, to develop further research Proofs of Concept for advanced predictive maintenance and other AI/ML applications pertaining to industrial applications, like for example secure KPI calculations (from data originating from industrial machinery) and secure SLA maps to optimise factory performance.
WINGS: Predictive maintenance and Digital Twins	WINGS will utilise CONFIDENTIAL6G solutions from this use case to further develop proof of concepts for predictive maintenance combined with federated AI/ML in the scope of Digital Twins for sensitive infrastructure assets.

7.6 USE CASE 2: CLOUD PRIVACY-PRESERVING CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING

Use case 2 produces automation procedures of secure VM initialization and configuration in cloud context. These procedures will be usable for many confidential computing applications, as a basic step of HW enablement. It will be especially useful for cloud providers that can offer this feature as a service. The exploitation strategy is provided for each organisation in the Table 9 below.

Target Group(s): Telecom operators, Service providers, Digital Technology developers.

Table 9. Exploitation plan and strategy: KER Proof of concept for Use Case 2: Privacy-preserving confidential computing platform that enables mitigation of internal threats for telecom cloud providers

Leading partner / Exploitation Asset	Exploitation Strategy
<p>UVC: Automation of TEE initialization and configuration</p>	<p>UVC will exploit CONFIDENTIAL6G use case #2 in two ways: 1) TEE initialization will be directly used in UVC's commercial product as a basis for preparing secure VMs in the cloud environment; 2) Automation of VM-based TEE initialization and configuration, alongside with support for confidential containers will be prototyped into a separate product that can be attractive to various cloud providers and will be marketed in that direction.</p>
<p>VTT: Attestation of telecom cloud services</p>	<p>VTT has developed and trialed telecommunication and trusted computing technologies and concepts for different security critical application domains. In CONFIDENTIAL6G, VTT develops capabilities to take the telecom cloud security into the next level. VTT will be able to help telecom cloud providers to assure and attest trustworthiness of their services and cloud users to deploy their services and data to verified external and cost-efficient cloud platforms. The capabilities will support emerging data federation (GAIA-X) frameworks. The project prototypes, publications, and other references will showcase our capabilities.</p>

7.7 USE CASE 3: INTELLIGENT CONNECTED VEHICLE

Connected vehicle use case will deliver an attack resilient communication, and computing environment with vehicles decentralised identities, immutable OEM updates anchored onto the blockchain, and federated learning shared between vehicles and infrastructure. The exploitation strategy is provided for each organisation in Table 10 below.

Target Group(s): Telecom operators, Service providers, Digital Technology developers, Partnerships, Society

Table 10. Exploitation plan and strategy: KER Proof of concept for Use Case 3: Intelligent connected vehicle, mission-critical services, OTA updates, FL/AI and vehicle to infrastructure communication

Leading partner / Exploitation Asset	Exploitation Strategy
<p>ZEN: Distributed Ledger Technology framework for vehicle identification and OTA updates</p>	<p>ZEN will exploit the knowledge gained in CONFIDENTIAL6G and integrate the resulting components and modules into the company's own solution. Most specifically, DID, DLT and Federated AI/ML will be deployed in the car client, and custom car modules to allow OTA operations with closed-loop systems developed by OEMs. Zentrix partners with onboard car system producer, which will be used as a ground for discussion of the exploitation strategy, to embed produced technology in existing car systems that currently experiments with Blockchain ledger that are less scalable and slower. The service will be deployed and offered to existing clients, as an extended upgraded service with licence including new features, including the device client.</p>
<p>TID: Secure, Private, Scalable, Hierarchical, Collaborative FL Modelling</p>	<p>TID will exploit the results of the third use case in the following ways: 1) TID will assess and investigate issues of secured and privacy-preserving communication and aggregation of models in the FL server in a connected-vehicles setting, as well as other settings that use FL technology for building privacy-preserving ML models. Based on these developments, TID will test ways to protect these settings from FL attacks such as membership inference, attribute inference, data reconstruction attacks, or data poisoning attacks, as well as possible side-channel attacks. 2) TID will use results and data produced from connected vehicles to drive emulations of FL model building when 5G or 6G infrastructure is being used, in order to optimise network connectivity using 5/6G antenna technology and hierarchical and scalable edge computing</p>

	<p>infrastructure. 3) TID will use the results from this use-case to make decisions on how to perform and tune serverless computing functions and containers to be more secure and privacy-preserving, while facilitating collaborative FL modelling across different third parties on the same local data.</p>
<p>WINGS: Intelligent and secure V2X communication</p>	<p>WINGS will leverage results from this use case in potential improvements, in terms of confidential communications, of its WINGSPARK (smart parking solution) and WINGSCHARIOT (secure/safe and trustworthy freight transportation)</p>

The exploitation of results mostly belongs to the business and commercialization domain which, similarly to science, tends to base its activity on comprehensive analysis, examination of the hypothesis, reaching certainty and achieving planned and expected results. As in science for that purpose, numerous kinds of methodologies, frameworks, tools and models are used, with the basic understanding that there is no perfect model and therefore in order to attain certainty using a multitude of them is the basic principle.

The purpose of the planned Tools and Methodologies for Exploitation of CONFIDENTIAL6G results is exactly to secure maximisation of the commercialization, use and sustainability of CONFIDENTIAL6G results by the scientific, economic, or public stakeholders, transforming R&I actions into concrete value and impact for society. The developed template (Figure 17) will be used within the CONFIDENTIAL6G to track the development status and characterise key exploitable results on the individual (partner) level.

	Organization Name	
Before	Background IP	
	Current market / existing customers	
	Current Exploitation Model	
During CONFIDENTIAL6G	Exploitable Result	
	Description of the Exploitable Result	
	Relation to Objectives	
	Relevant Performance Improvement Targets	
	Relevant WP/Task/Deliverable	
	IPR Protection Method	
	Ownership	
	Type of exploitation	
	Current/Expected TRL	
	Target market(s)	
	Size and growth outlook of target market(s)	
	Target customer segments	
	Competitors	
	Competitive advantages compared to SOTA (state of the art)	
	Key partners	
Envisaged pricing model		
Envisaged Sales price and Profit		
Other useful links/information		

Figure 17. Key exploitable result characterisation template

To determine the viability and potential of each exploitable result, we will conduct a detailed market analysis. This analysis takes into account factors such as market size, challenges, available solutions, customer segments, and the economic environment. By gaining valuable insights into customer needs, competition, and regulatory environments, we can make informed decisions on how to exploit our results effectively.

Based on the outcomes of market analysis and feasibility assessment, we make strategic decisions on the best approach to exploit our results. This may involve industrial use, patenting, technology transfer, or publication. We consider factors such as potential partnerships, licensing agreements, and business models to maximise the impact and reach of our innovations.

Active collaboration with European technical initiatives is a priority for us. We engage with and contribute to standardization technical committees, working groups, and open-source communities of developers. This collaborative approach fosters cooperation, facilitates the seamless integration of our technology into the broader European landscape, and enhances the market potential of our results.

Within our exploitation strategy, we will develop and update as a part of the deliverables D6.2 and D6.3 a business model that outlines how we plan to generate revenue and sustain the commercial exploitation of our outcomes. The business model encompasses professional-oriented services supported by our core framework, as well as audience-centric services that enable the generation and sharing of new tools and experiences. We favour open-source policies and adopt a dual-licensing approach to manage the knowledge produced internally while also exposing specific knowledge to the scientific community.

While the initial Business Plan is drafted at the proposal stage, a detailed plan is developed and refined within the project activities. This plan outlines the specific steps, activities, and timelines for the commercial exploitation of our outcomes in the medium to long term. It serves as a dynamic observatory and scoreboard, allowing us to monitor and update our progress toward achieving market outreach maturity.

By implementing this detailed exploitation strategy, we aim to transform our project's outcomes into real-world impact. Through careful analysis, intellectual property management, and strategic decision-making, we unlock the full potential of our innovations, driving positive change and creating value for various stakeholders.

INNOVATION RADAR

To effectively capture and showcase the project's innovative outcomes, CONFIDENTIAL6G intends to leverage the Innovation Radar platform. Through this strategic utilisation, the project aims to highlight its innovations and gain visibility within the innovation ecosystem. Innovation Radar, a powerful platform for identifying and promoting EU-funded innovations, offers CONFIDENTIAL6G a valuable opportunity to demonstrate its technological advancements and their potential societal impact.

8 IPR KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT

The management of intellectual property rights is a crucial element of our strategy for maximising the value of our innovations. We place great emphasis on establishing clear guidelines for identifying, owning, and granting access rights to our research outcomes. This approach ensures that our intellectual property is adequately protected while promoting collaboration and knowledge sharing within the consortium. We also recognize the importance of timely publication to safeguard European intellectual property rights.

CONFIDENTIAL6G acknowledges the importance of safeguarding and leveraging intellectual property (IP) and underscores three key components of an effective system. Firstly, we prioritise the establishment of a comprehensive IP protection framework that encompasses patents, copyrights, branding, and industrial design. This framework is designed to provide clarity regarding ownership and usage rights, as well as facilitate the transferability and publication of IP. Secondly, we recommend the integration of a technology transfer framework, ideally supported by specialised knowledge transfer offices staffed with experienced professionals, such as the European IPR Helpdesk. Lastly, a fair and robust legal enforcement system in each partner's jurisdiction is vital for efficient dispute resolution, penalty imposition, and the application of appropriate sanctions.

The Consortium Agreement will specifically address and resolve any IP-related issues that may arise. Our fundamental principle regarding IP ownership stipulates that any knowledge generated by a project partner belongs to that partner. In cases where joint development makes it impossible to distinguish individual contributions, joint ownership will be assumed unless the involved parties agree to an alternative arrangement. Concerning background IP, access rights will generally be granted without royalties for project-related activities, unless otherwise specified prior to signing the Grant Agreement.

Aligned with the project's objectives and the partners' interests in industrial exploitation, CONFIDENTIAL6G partners will file patents in areas where they contribute to advancing the state-of-the-art, particularly in the field of collaborative, privacy-preserving hierarchical federated learning.

9 CONCLUSION

This document presents a comprehensive strategy for effectively communicating the project's outcomes to various target groups, raising awareness, and inspiring action. The dissemination and communication plan creates a variety of methods to disseminate results, including the CONFIDENTIAL6G website, guidelines, training materials, flyers, brochures, peer-reviewed publications, policy briefs, position statements, non-scientific publications, MOOCs, videos, blogs, webinars, conferences, workshops, newsletters, email campaigns, and open access repositories for research. The plan also highlights the importance of creating focus groups of external experts from different domains to enhance their involvement with the CONFIDENTIAL6G project. The communication strategy is developed for implementing campaigns so as to promote the project and its achievements to the target audience, utilizing existing networks and ecosystems to facilitate effective communication. The CONFIDENTIAL6G website serves as a central tool for disseminating project information, providing a platform for sharing updates, engaging with target groups, and increasing project visibility. The plan also emphasizes the significance of leveraging social media platforms like LinkedIn and X for researchers to connect with peers, exchange ideas, and disseminate their work. Additionally, the deliverable addresses the exploitation strategy, which will adapt to the scientific and technological progress and be based on collective and individual exploitation strategies and activities. The Consortium Agreement will define the intellectual property rights (IPR) management strategy, which will significantly influence the exploitation approach. The final version of the exploitation plan will provide a strategy for sustaining the partners' outcomes beyond the project's completion. It is important to note that the dissemination, communication, and exploitation plans are dynamic documents that will be continuously updated to align with the project's progress. They will be modified as necessary to enhance and expand the project's outreach to target groups, ensuring effective communication of the CONFIDENTIAL6G vision.